

Synthesis of Some 3-Fluorinatedaryl-4-Alkyl-/Aryl-5-Mercapto-1,2,4-Triazoles and Related Compounds as Possible CNS Depressants

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1-Fluoroaroyl-4-alkyl-/aryl thiosemicarbazides have been synthesised and cyclized into corresponding 3-fluorinatedaryl-4-alkyl-/aryl-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazoles. A few of these compounds have been alkylated at position-5. A representative number of compounds have been screened for CNS depressant activity and four compounds, viz: 3-(4'-fluorophenyl)-4-*n*-hexyl-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazole, 3-(4'-fluorophenyl)-4-(4'-fluorophenyl)-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazole, 3-(4'-fluorophenyl)-4-(4'-ethoxyphenyl)-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazole and 3-(3'-fluorophenyl)-4-(4'-chlorophenyl)-5-benzylthio-1, 2, 4-triazole have been found to possess some activity.

THIOSEMICARBAZIDES, having an acyl group in position-1 and an aryl group in position-4, have been reported to possess good antitubercular activity¹⁻⁴ and antifungal activity⁵. On cyclization, these compounds yield 3,4-disubstituted-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazoles. The triazole nucleus itself, has been associated with diverse biological activities⁶⁻⁹. In connection with our work on biologically active substituted-1, 2, 4-triazoles¹⁰, we now report the synthesis of a number of 1-fluoroaroyl-4-alkyl/aryl substituted thiosemicarbazides (I) and 3-fluorinatedaryl 4-alkyl-aryl-5-mercapto-/alkylthio-1, 2, 4-triazoles of the type II.

A representative number of compounds have been screened on the following parameters, viz;

- (i) Screening on central Nervous system.
- (ii) Screening on cardiovascular system, and four of the compounds (Nos. 9,10, 15 & 17; Table 2) have been found to exhibit fair activity.

Experimental

The fluorinated acidhydrazides were obtained by the condensation of appropriate ethyl esters with 95% hydrazine hydrate by the method of Curtius and Trachmann¹¹.

The fluorinated ethyl esters were obtained from appropriate toluidines by converting them first into respective fluorotoluenes by Schiemann reaction; the later being then oxidised and esterified.

The alkyl and arylisothiocyanates were prepared by the method of Dains et al¹².

1-(2'-Fluorobenzoyl)-4-*n*-hexylthiosemicarbazide :

2-Fluorobenzoic acid hydrazide (1.54g., 0.01 mole) was taken in a 50 ml round bottomed flask and 10 ml of dioxan was then added. The contents were refluxed till a clear solution was obtained. *n*-Hexylisothiocyanate (1.57g., 0.011 mole) was then poured through condenser followed by 5 ml of dioxan and the mixture further refluxed for 3 hrs. After cooling, the solidified mass was filtered and washed, first with cold dioxan, and finally with ether. The crude product (2.5g, 80%) was purified by crystallization from ethanol to get the desired product¹³ m.p. 136°-38° (Found : S, 10.22. C₁₄H₂₀FN₃OS requires S. 10.77%).

All other substituted thiosemicarbazides were prepared in a similar manner. The properties and analytical data of the synthesised compounds are listed in Table 1.

3-(2'-Fluorophenyl)-4-*n*-hexyl-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazole :

1-(2'-Fluorobenzoyl)-4-*n*-hexylthiosemicarbazide (2.97g., 0.01 mole) and 2*N* sodium hydroxide (20 ml) were refluxed for 2 hrs. The solution was cooled and acidified to litmus with dilute hydrochloric acid. The desired compound, thus precipitated, was filtered,

TABLE I

1-FLUOROARYL-4-ALKYL-/ARYLTIOSEMICARBAZIDES

S. No.	R	Nature of R ¹	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	% Sulphur Found	% Sulphur Reqd.
1.	2-F	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	80	136-8	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ FN ₃ OS	10.22	10.77
2.	2-F	4-Fluorophenyl	83	151-3	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ F ₂ N ₃ OS	10.05	10.42
3.	2-F	4-Chlorophenyl	90	163-4	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ClFN ₃ OS	9.67	9.89
4.	2-F	4-Bromophenyl	92	177-8	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ BrFN ₃ OS	8.22	8.70
5.	3-F	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	84	158-60	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ FN ₃ OS	10.38	10.77
6.	3-F	4-Fluorophenyl	88	134-36	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ F ₂ N ₃ OS	10.21	10.42
7.	3-F	4-Chlorophenyl	88	161-2	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ClFN ₃ OS	9.61	9.89
8.	3-F	4-Bromophenyl	93	164-6	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ BrFN ₃ OS	8.29	8.70
9.	4-F	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	85	150-2	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ FN ₃ OS	10.33	10.77
10.	4-F	4-Fluorophenyl	89	171-2	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ F ₂ N ₃ OS	10.21	10.42
11.	4-F	4-Chlorophenyl	92	158-61	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ClFN ₃ OS	9.54	9.89
12.	4-F	4-Bromophenyl	77	154-6	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ BrFN ₃ OS	8.23	8.70
13.	4-F	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	81	167-8	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ FN ₃ OS	8.54	8.94
14.	4-F	4-Methylphenyl	86	164-6	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ FN ₃ OS	10.32	10.56
15.	4-F	4-Ethoxyphenyl	83	155-7	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ FN ₃ O ₂ S	9.33	9.61

washed and dried. The crude product (2.49g., 85%) was then purified by crystallization from aqueous ethanol¹⁴, m.p. 58°-60°. (Found : S, 11.17. C₁₄H₁₈FN₃S requires S, 11.47%).

The other triazoles were prepared in a similar manner by cyclization of corresponding 1,4-disubstituted thiosemicarbazides. The synthesised compounds with their properties and analytical data are recorded in Table 2.

3-(3'-Fluorophenyl)-4-(4'-chlorophenyl)-5-ethylthio-1,2,4-triazole :

3-(3'-Fluorophenyl)-4-(4'-chlorophenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (0.01 mole) was heated in 10 ml *N* NaOH at 60°-70° with 1.0g. ethylbromide. The solution was then diluted by adding 20 ml alcohol and again heated for some time. On cooling, the desired product was precipitated, which was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to afford 1.52g. (70%) of the compound¹⁵ (Found : S, 9.38. C₁₆H₁₃ClFN₃S requires S, 9.57%)

The other alkyl and arylthio derivatives of various triazoles were prepared in a similar manner. Their yields, m.ps. and analytical data are given in Table 2.

Biological Activity

The test compounds were used as solution in aqueous ethanol. Animals used were mice and the volume of drug injected did not exceed 6 ml/10 mg of body weight. 13 of these compounds (Nos. 1 to 6, 9, 10, 13, 15, 16, 17 & 18) listed in Table 2 were screened for their CNS depressant activity and on cardiovascular system.

Screening on central nervous system :

Gross behavioral changes. A decrease in motor activity was observed with compound Nos. 1, 2, 9 & 17 at 500 mg/kg I.P. dose, with No. 10 at 100 mg/kg

I.P., and with No. 18 at 250 mg/kg intraperitoneally. With compound Nos. 1, 2, 17 & 18, the animal appeared depressed and had micturation. The animals treated with Nos. 9 & 10 were markedly hypertensive to external stimuli (sound & touch) and lead to clonic and tonic convulsions and ultimately death. Righting response in mice was observed with No. 15 at 100 mg/kg I.P. dose.

Compound Nos. 3, 4, 5, 6, 13 and 16 were found ineffective upto the dose level of 500 mg/kg I.P.

Acute toxicity. Only compounds Nos. 9, 10 & 17 were lethal. At 100 mg/kg dose level, No. 17 caused marked respiratory depression in the animals resulting in cyanosis and death. Other compounds were not lethal even upto 100 mg/kg dose level.

Compound Nos. 1-6, 9, 10, 13 & 15 were found to possess no activity regarding pentobarbitone sleeping time, metrazol induced convulsions, maximal electric shock convulsions and amphetamine toxicity in group mice upto 500 mg/kg I.P. dose.

Compound No. 18 increased the pentobarbitone sleeping time significantly to 50.5 mins at the dose of 500 mg/kg whereas control was 16.4 minutes.

Screening on cardiovascular system. Compound Nos. 1-6, when given upto the dose of 20 mg/kg had significant hypotensive effect which varied in degree with the drug used. All the drugs increased respiration and decreased intensive mobility.

The results of the above screening are not adequate to suggest a structure activity correlation.

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TABLE 2.

3,4-DISUBSTITUTED-5-MERCAPTO/ALKYLTHIO-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOLES

S. No.	R	R ¹	R ²	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	% Sulphur	
							Found	Reqd.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1.	2-F	n-Hexyl	H	85	58-60	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ FN ₃ S	11.17	11.47
2.	2-F	4-Fluorophenyl	H	83	150-2	C ₁₄ H ₉ F ₂ N ₃ S	10.78	11.07
3.	2-F	4-Chlorophenyl	H	87	200-2	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClFN ₃ S	10.23	10.47
4.	2-F	4-Bromophenyl	H	89	253-4	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrFN ₃ S	8.86	9.14
5.	3-F	n-Hexyl	H	88	83-4	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ FN ₃ S	11.17	11.47
6.	3-F	4-Fluorophenyl	H	90	233-5	C ₁₄ H ₉ F ₂ N ₃ S	10.64	11.07
7.	3-F	4-Chlorophenyl	H	85	201-2	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClFN ₃ S	10.08	10.47
8.	3-F	4-Bromophenyl	H	88	215-7	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrFN ₃ S	8.77	9.14
9.	3-F	4-Chlorophenyl	Ethyl	70	128-30	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClFN ₃ S	9.38	9.57
10.	3-F	4-Chlorophenyl	Benzyl	64	168-70	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ClFN ₃ S	7.84	8.12
11.	3-F	4-Fluorophenyl	Benzyl	76	141-3	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ F ₂ N ₃ S	8.22	8.46
12.	4-F	n-Hexyl	H	83	81-3	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ FN ₃ S	11.11	11.47
13.	4-F	4-Fluorophenyl	H	84	175-7	C ₁₄ H ₉ F ₂ N ₃ S	10.83	11.07
14.	4-F	4-Chlorophenyl	H	91	191-3	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClFN ₃ S	10.09	10.47
15.	4-F	4-Bromophenyl	H	77	180-2	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrFN ₃ S	8.86	9.14
16.	4-F	3, 4-Dichlorophenyl	H	86	183-5	C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₂ FN ₃ S	8.89	9.31
17.	4-F	4-Methylphenyl	H	90	225-7	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ FN ₃ S	11.04	11.22
18.	4-F	4-Ethoxyphenyl	H	91	185-7	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ FN ₃ OS	9.78	10.16

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